

Pathways to Interdisciplinary and Transdisciplinary Research: the SHAPE-ID Toolkit

Find tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Develop a career in inter- and transdisciplinary research

Abstract

Early-stage researchers, in particular, can receive very mixed messages about the wisdom of pursuing an inter- or transdisciplinary research career which is often regarded as high risk within a research system that is still primarily structured on discipline-based evaluation and recognition criteria. Success may require a more tactical approach to career development.

This publication compiles resources collected as part of the SHAPE-ID project to support researchers, funders/policymakers, research organisations and societal partners to develop career pathways in inter- and trans-disciplinary research.

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Online source – SHAPE-ID Toolkit

This publication is an extract of the SHAPE-ID Toolkit. For a general overview, visit: [10.5281/zenodo.4743703](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743703).

The Toolkit provides tools and resources to make informed decisions about interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research with the Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences, the Sciences, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics, and societal partners.

Contributors & Co-producers

The SHAPE-ID resource collection series is an artefact of collective wisdom. Some resources were generated by the SHAPE-ID team, but many were already available online and the toolkit acts as a gateway to locate them. The SHAPE-ID collection series is based on discussions with and inputs from the SHAPE-ID consortium members, namely Anna Buchner, Maureen Burgess, Bianca Vienni Baptista, Caitriona Curtis, Isabel Fletcher, Giorgia Galvini, Catherine Lyall, Maciej Maryl, Jane Ohlmeyer, Christian Pohl, Andrea Ricci, Carlo Sessa, Jack Spaapen, Sibylle Studer, Doireann Wallace, Piotr Wciślik, Keisha Taylor Wesselink, Declan Whelan-Curtin.

SHAPE-ID resource collection series

- Understand inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743671](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743671)
- Develop collaborative conditions: [10.5281/zenodo.4743673](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743673)
- Co-create a research project: [10.5281/zenodo.4743675](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743675)
- Fund collaborative research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743677](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743677)
- Evaluate inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743679](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743679)
- Disseminate inter- and transdisciplinary research findings: [10.5281/zenodo.4743683](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743683)
- Improve inter- and transdisciplinary research skills: [10.5281/zenodo.4743685](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743685)
- Support collaborative researchers: [10.5281/zenodo.4743687](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743687)
- Develop a career in inter- and transdisciplinary research: [10.5281/zenodo.4743689](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743689)

Develop a Career in Inter- and Transdisciplinary Research

Early stage researchers, in particular, can receive very mixed messages about the wisdom of pursuing an interdisciplinary research career which is often regarded as high risk within a research system that is still primarily structured on discipline-based evaluation and recognition criteria. Success may require a more tactical approach to career development.

Resource highlights

- ▶ SHAPE-ID Top Ten Tips for inter- and transdisciplinary careers: [10.5281/zenodo.4743693](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743693)
- ▶ SHAPE-ID Top Ten Tips for mentoring for academic careers: [10.5281/zenodo.4743693](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4743693)

Subtopics

Create an ID/TD CV

Build and sustain a career as an ID/TD researcher

Develop a network

Supervise an ID/TD PhD

Resources per subtopics

Create an ID/TD CV [▲](#)

Interdisciplinary researchers may find it challenging to demonstrate their contributions when reward processes have traditionally been founded on discipline-based structures. An interdisciplinary researcher's publication list may seem less cohesive than that of colleagues whose work is firmly located within one discipline. They may publish in a wider variety of journals, possibly in newer journals or those not considered 'mainstream'. In larger interdisciplinary teams, researchers can sometimes find it challenging to demonstrate their individual contributions. Prescriptive formats for academic CVs/Resumes may not sufficiently highlight positive indicators of interdisciplinary achievement such as research collaborations, joint publications or reviewing requests from a wide-range of funding bodies and journals. Wherever possible, try to incorporate additional narrative in any recommended CV template to explain an interdisciplinary approach and contributions.

An example of a possible narrative structure is the Royal Society's *Resume for Researchers*.

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Build and sustain a career as an ID/TD researcher [▲](#)

Many publications discuss the career risks and benefits for those who pursue interdisciplinary research, especially from the perspective of early career researchers. In this SHAPE-ID blog post, Jennifer Edmond shares some of the frustrations of being an interdisciplinary academic.

[VISIT SITE](#)

In this short video, current and former students of the Science and Policy PhD programme at the Plant Science Center in Switzerland talk about their experiences of transdisciplinary research including key challenges and lessons learnt.

[WATCH VIDEO](#)

Catherine Lyall and her co-authors have written about this in two briefing notes. The first addresses interdisciplinary careers.

[READ PDF](#)

And the second addresses challenges of research management.

[READ PDF](#)

Chapter 6 of the book *Charting a Course for an Interdisciplinary Career* gives practical advice on establishing and sustaining interdisciplinary careers in and beyond universities.

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SHAPE-ID partner Catherine Lyall provides her top ten tips for ID/TD academic careers.

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Develop a network [▲](#)

The way an academic is viewed professionally is reflected by their peer network but a researcher pursuing multiple interests may have multiple and shifting peer networks. Many universities offer staff training in academic networking.

This Open Access article written by a group of early career researchers discusses how to promote a series of “encounters” to help develop an interdisciplinary career.

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This guide for early career researchers who identify as interdisciplinary researchers provides an overview of some of the most commonly perceived opportunities and challenges of doing and being an interdisciplinary researcher, including practical advice on building your networks.

[READ PDF](#)

The theme of finding time and space for informal discussions with colleagues is a persistent one in modern academia. The importance of informal networks and shared physical spaces are often overlooked by institutions and their value has been especially highlighted by the travel restrictions during the Covid-19 pandemic. For an architect's view, read this short magazine article.

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This blogpost describes what the transdisciplinary research community, including early career researchers, wants from a global and virtual community. The research was conducted as part of the development of the tdAcademy online portal.

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Supervise an ID/TD PhD [▲](#)

The nature of PhD research varies greatly between disciplines and between institutions: a PhD thesis may take the form of a monograph or consist of a set of published journal articles; a PhD candidate may work on their own or as part of a team; they may be expected to generate their own research topic and research questions or these may be specified by their supervisor as part of a larger research study; PhD scholars may be seen as students or as members of staff. What then happens when a PhD candidate straddles two or more disciplinary traditions and what does this mean for the academics who supervise them?

Catherine Lyall and colleagues have worked with PhD researchers to produce a short Guide to Supervising an ID PhD.

[READ PDF](#)

We recommend reading Stephanie Pfirman and Melissa Begg's short article

Troubled by Interdisciplinarity?

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This fictionalised scenario has been used in workshops to prompt discussions about good supervisory practice.

[READ PDF](#)

In the US, the Integrative Graduate Education and Research Traineeship (IGERT) pioneered a novel, collaborative form of PhD training that has left a legacy of featured stories and a library of articles to inspire doctoral research.

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